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EMPLOYEE'S SATISFACTION TOWARDS WELFARE MEASURES IN INDIAN RAILWAYS: A STUDY OF SELECT RAILWAY EMPLOYEES IN SECUNDRABAD

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Abstract

Welfare measures improve the mental and moral health and efficiency of workers. They assist in maintenance of industrial peace. According to Sri H.S. Kirkadly, the whole field of welfare is one in much can be done to combat the sense of frustration of the industrial worker, to relieve him of personal and family worries, to improve his health to afford him means of self expression to offer him some sphere in which he can excel others and to help him to a wider conception of life welfare measures do not only bestows benefit to the workers but these also pay immediately and in the long run the benefits to employers as well. As for example a suitable working condition does not only make workers lead a healthy life conducive to the growth of his development but is also pays the employer in making a good turn over.

This paper aims to study different welfare measures given by Indian railways to its employees and find out the employees satisfaction levels towards different welfare measures given by Indian railways. Innovative suggestions for improvement of welfare measures were found out.

Keywords: Welfare Organization, Employee's Satisfaction, Health and Efficiency of Workers

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INTRODUCTION:

Welfare measures improve the mental and moral health and efficiency of workers. They assist in maintenance of industrial peace. According to Sri H.S. Kirkadly, the whole field of welfare is one in much can be done to combat the sense of frustration of the industrial worker, to relieve him of personal and family worries, to improve his health to afford him means of self expression to offer him some sphere in which he can excel others and to help him to a wider conception of life welfare measures do not only bestows benefit to the workers but these also pay immediately and in the long run the benefits to employers as well. As for example a suitable working condition does not only make workers lead a healthy life conducive to the growth of his development but is also pays the employer in making a good turn over.

The Rege Committee observed that welfare included anything done for intellectual, physical, moral, and economical betterment of worker, the employer or the government or any other agency over and above what was laid down by law or what was normally expected as part of any contractual benefit. Welfare measures are designed to effect an all round improvement in the employees working and living condition.

WELFARE ORGANIZATION IN RAILWAYS:

Welfare measures are governed by Workmen Compensation Act 1923. Later the Act was amended and known as The Indian Railways Act 1956. Pass rules are governed by 1986 pass rules.

Welfare organization is functioning in each railway to see to the welfare of the staff. The Chief personnel officer is the head of this organization. A senior personnel officer is posted as welfare Officer in the head quarters of each railway to look after the day to day work of the organization. He is assisted by a number of welfare inspectors. In the Division/Workshops, the DRM/Divl, Supdt/S.W./Dy. Chief Mechanical Engineer is in- charge of the organization. The Divisional/Workshop Personnel Officer supervises the work of the organization and he is assisted in his work by an Asst. Personnel Officer/Welfare Officer. In divisions/workshops also welfare inspectors are posted to look after the welfare of the staff.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Numerous research studies on welfare measures and reasons thereof have as the following experts shows ended in a number of very interesting findings we view welfare measures as emerging from a variety factors including characteristics of welfare measures. The researcher wants to provide literature review of the subject issue with a discussion of current thinking on welfare measures and its satisfaction by employees in work place. Welfare measures improve moral of employees and they have impact on job satisfaction and performance of employees.

Terry emphasized upon behavioral aspects of supervision, up to date and inclusive treatment of supervisory subject areas. It explains what the supervisor now does and what

tools, knowledge, and skills he requires. An analysis of the social and motivational basis of work in Tata Steel has been attempted by Pandey "The analysis shifts the level from the organization to the individual and maps how the worker, the supervisor, and the manager located in various groups of 25 departments view the work, leadership nature of the job, incentives communication, worker's involvement, target satisfaction etc. this sequential shift from the philosophy, heritage, technology, through organizational systems to individual level socio-motivational factors of work, is meant to give an elaborate account of what human factors in Tata steel mean".

Bhatia primarily focuses in the new changes in practices that are taking place in the personnel function. He discusses areas, such as, the new role of the personnel units: results orientation in personnel function: concept of organization development: utilization of human resources: career planning: promotion: performance appraisal: counseling which will meet the need and overwhelming concern for improving productivity and better utilization of human resources in the plants". Martins conducted a study on "welfare at work". He has focused attention on the areas of Personnel and Group Welfare. He says the first will be given pride of place, because personal problems most need specialist help. Group Welfare is by its nature more of team effort. The main driving force coming from volunteers who will none the less need expert help from time to time. He says organizations may provide over and above the requirements of such legislation as the Factories acts and the offices, but inspection should ensure that they do not drop below the minimum. In considering priorities above the minima, managers could well give thought to the priority of physiological needs of men and women. Adequate lavatories, adequate in quality as well as in quantity, should be the prime consideration.

Saigal argued in his study on "Dynamics of Labour management Interaction" That a system of participative management can be profitably utilized as a means for promoting human relation and facilitate the greater emotional and physical involvement of workers. It also results in the creation of a working class more firmly committed to the industrial environment and

one which promote amity and goodwill. Laxmi Narain conducted a national survey on workers participation. He surveyed over 2500 managers and 300 trade unionists in 40 central govt industrial public enterprises, evaluating the attitudes, approaches of managers and trade unionists to participate. He argued that for participation to succeed both the management and unions will have to have a fresh approach and an enlightened outlook. Virmani conducted an analysis of 28 organizations in the country, he attempted to study an in-depth analysis of the participative management Vs collective bargaining and found "A lot of lip sympathy is aid to the introduction of participative management, and on the other, there is a growing feeling among the trade unionists and the managements that collective bargaining van in itself be as system whereby the employees van have a say in the affairs of the management".

Mukerjee Kumarappa and jagannatham stressed the need for a comprehensive system of social security. Kumarappa emphasized programmers of assistance to the unemployed, the aged, the physically handicapped and the neglected dependent children and women. Keni, Abhyankar, Agarwal, and Idgunji published books on social insurance. The general approach and methodology fallowed by these authors were the same. With the differences in emphasis, the nature of social insurance programmers and their development in other countries formed the praised matter of their discussion introduction in India, and the problem connected there to were also discussed by them. The adarkar report constitutes the most important on social security as it formed the basis of the employee state insurance scheme, which was enacted in 1948. Punekar's book the problem of social security for the seaman was studied by saxena¹⁸for his doctoral thesis and also by adarkar and Bodmer. The labor investigation committee made a detailed study of the risks which bring about the insecurity to the workers, and the need and the methods for meeting such risks. Social security received greater importance in the post 1947 era. As free India included the provisions of social security in the directive principles of state policy, which have been incorporated in the country's constitution adopted in 1949. The establishment of the employees' state insurance scheme and the coal mines provident fund scheme in the year 1948

provided material for research and at the same time encouraged the study of the need and feasibility of other programmers.

Jagannadham chansarkar and agarwal dealt with various aspects of social insurance in India Mehta, prabhat Chandra, arora and moorthy have also dealt with the system extensively. The study group on social security submitted a significant report recommending a unified system of social insurance for industrial workers and the conversion of the provident fund scheme into that of a gratuity- cum-pension scheme. Laxmi Narain, AnandRao, Sankar and Geeta Gouri and Suryaprakash have studied the various aspects of the governance of PEs. Their studies revealed that Parliamentary control needed to be strengthened as it had not been effective because of the constraints of time, expertise and interest in the working of the PEs on the part of the Members of the Parliament. Mishra, Sankar, Ravishankar and Sai intensively studied revealed that PEs had fallen behind the expectations, while doing so, full credit was given to the improvement in the performance of PEs, their relative performance with private enterprises and their total factor productivity.

.A general review of the articles referred to above leads us to a number of interesting and significant conclusions. There are quite a large number of articles dealing with various aspects of social security in India. Industrial workers, no doubt continue to the main concern of social security programs and researches, but the needs and problems of the other vulnerable groups of populations also began to receive to attention. Social insurance has been the subject of a large of number of articles which taken together provide a comprehensive coverage. Article on health and maternity and work injure insurance are primarily demoted to an examination and review of the employees state insurance scheme.

RESEARCH GAP:

Research was done till now on weather employee satisfaction towards welfare measures effect productivity and weather welfare measures have positive effect to employers. The present research tries to find out employee satisfaction levels towards welfare measures and different

welfare measures given to railway employees their by suggesting measures to improve welfare measures with which employees are not satisfied.

RESEARCH PROBLEM:

To study different welfare measures given by Indian railways to its employees and find out the employees satisfaction levels towards different welfare measures given by Indian railways. Innovative suggestions for improvement of welfare measures were found out.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To study different welfare measures given by railways to its employees in the select area of study.
2. To identify welfare measures with which employees are dissatisfied.
3. To know about any other welfare measures needed by employees.
4. To know about the different welfare measures provided by Indian railways.

HYPOTHESIS:

Null Hypothesis: “that the employees are not satisfied with the welfare facilities of Indian railways”

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This research assignment attempts to find the employees satisfaction towards welfare measures provided by Indian railways. Primary data is collected through questionnaires which are be given personally to railway employees. Secondary data giving information on various welfare measures is collected from

1. Railway year book
2. Guide to railway men book
3. Websites relating to railways
4. Newspapers

Population : All the Railway Employees in the Secunderabad Area

Sample area : Mettuguda Area in Secunderabad.

Sample Size : 300 Employees.

Sampling Method : Convenience.

Tools For analysis : Percentages, Tables, and Graphs etc.

The study was undertaken during the January 10th and June 10th. 6 months time was needed to collect primary data, secondary data and analyze the data

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The study includes a description of all welfare measures given by Indian railways to its employees and also provisions given in office. The study lists out various welfare measures provided Indian railways like -privilege passes- PTO's (privilege ticket order) -staff quarters - educational facilities - railway schools - railway junior colleges - railway degree colleges - medical facilities - railway hospitals - dispensaries -welfare measures provided by Indian railway women's organizations cooperative credit society activities, recreational facilities - sports provided by Indian railways - library facilities to employee children's - function halls -merit scholarships provided by CCS and railways women organization to employees children - student passes given by Indian railways to employee children for attending college -school - housing projects undertaken by IRWO -meritorious service awards given by Indian railways -productivity bonus given by railways -housing loans to employees -vehicle loans to staff -festival advance -pension - gratuity to railway employees -canteen facilities in offices -lunch room facilities in railway offices - drinking water facilities in offices - other welfare measures.

The study also consists of collecting primary data regarding satisfaction of employees to welfare measures given by Indian railways and data analysis. Research provides insight into the employee satisfaction towards welfare measures given to railway men. It also leads to important conclusions and suggestions which will be benefit the railway organization and railway employees.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

The employee Welfare variable consist of Twenty eight sub-variables in four point rating scale. The application of factor analysis over these Twenty eight variables derived the following results:

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.942
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	21412.521
	df	378
	Sig.	.000

From the above table it is found that KMO value 0.942 and Bartlett's test of Sphericity with approximate Chi-Square value 21412.521 are statistically significant at 5% level. It denotes the sample is adequate to represent the factors of employee welfare. The Twenty eight variables obtain considerable variance to represent the satisfaction level of employees.

The following communality table indicates the range of variance exhibiting by Twenty eight variables of employee welfare.

components	Initial	Extraction
Satisfaction towards Privilege Passes	1.000	.719
Response on Indian Railways PTO's	1.000	.620
satisfaction levels on Railway Staff Quarters	1.000	.920
satisfaction levels about Railway Schools	1.000	.914
Feelings about Railway Junior Colleges	1.000	.911
Satisfaction levels on Degree Colleges	1.000	.918
satisfaction rate about Medical facilities	1.000	.887
Response rate about Welfare measures to women	1.000	.835
Satisfaction rate about Cooperative Credit Society	1.000	.922

Response rate about Recreational facilities/sports	1.000	.957
Satisfaction rate about Library facilities to their children	1.000	.901
Satisfaction rate about the Function Halls	1.000	.880
Merit Scholarships provided by CCS and Railways Women's Organization to their children	1.000	.924
Satisfaction rate about the Student passes to their children	1.000	.874
Satisfaction on Housing projects undertaken by IRWO	1.000	.906
Satisfaction rate about the Meritorious Service Awards given by Indian Railways to their children	1.000	.946
Satisfaction rate about the Productivity Bonus	1.000	.942
Satisfaction rate about the Housing Loans	1.000	.938
Satisfaction rate about the Vehicle Loans	1.000	.952
Satisfaction levels towards the Festival advance /Loan	1.000	.959
Vehicle Parking facilities in office	1.000	.859
Retirement benefits like pension, gratuity... et	1.000	.749
welfare measures of Indian Railways when compared to other organizations like Defense, Airways, APSRTC.....etc	1.000	.908
different welfare measures provided by Indian Railways	1.000	.867
feelings about those Indian Railways in No.1 in providing excellent welfare measures to its employees as a whole	1.000	.962
Canteen facilities provided in office	1.000	.915
Lunch Room facilities	1.000	.955
Drinking water facilities	1.000	.957
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

From the above table it is found that the variance ranges from 0.620 to 0.962. It denotes the variance of the variable ranges from 62% to 96.2%. This variance designates the formation of significant factors.

The following total variance table indicates the individual and cumulative variance of the derived factors:

Table-3 Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigen values			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	22.286	79.594	79.594	10.096	36.058	36.058
2	1.447	5.167	84.761	7.628	27.243	63.301
3	1.263	4.510	89.271	7.272	25.970	89.271
4	.796	2.842	92.113			
5	.480	1.716	93.829			
6	.348	1.243	95.072			
7	.252	.898	95.970			
8	.198	.707	96.677			
9	.175	.625	97.302			
10	.150	.536	97.838			
11	.133	.473	98.311			
12	.085	.305	98.616			
13	.085	.304	98.921			
14	.059	.212	99.132			
15	.037	.134	99.266			
16	.034	.122	99.388			
17	.026	.092	99.479			
18	.024	.087	99.566			
19	.022	.080	99.646			
20	.019	.067	99.713			
21	.016	.059	99.771			
22	.014	.050	99.821			
23	.013	.047	99.868			
24	.011	.041	99.909			

25	.009	.031	99.940			
26	.008	.027	99.967			
27	.006	.020	99.986			
28	.004	.014	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

From the above table it is found that the fourteen factors are reduced into six predominant factors with individual variance 36.058, 27.243, 25.970, and cumulative variance is 89.271. These variances are significant to individually considering derived factors.

The following Rotated Component Matrix (a) indicates the variable composition of the factors:

Table-4 Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component		
	1	2	3
VAR00020	.845		
VAR00025	.836		
VAR00027	.818		
VAR00018	.817		
VAR00017	.804		
VAR00019	.796		
VAR00010	.782		
VAR00028	.758		
VAR00016	.743		
VAR00013	.706		
VAR00024	.627		
VAR00022	.560		
VAR00003		.843	
VAR00021		.788	
VAR00011		.745	

VAR00002		.733	
VAR00001		.683	
VAR00007		.635	
VAR00015		.631	
VAR00023		.613	
VAR00026		.609	
VAR00009			.830
VAR00014			.820
VAR00004			.776
VAR00005			.738
VAR00006			.734
VAR00008			.715
VAR00012			.606

- a. Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
- b. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
- c. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.

From the above table it is found that the first factor consist of –

- Satisfaction levels towards the Festival advance /Loan **(0.845)**
- feelings about those Indian Railways in No.1 in providing excellent welfare measures to its employees as a whole **(0.836)**
- Lunch Room facilities **(0.818)**
- Satisfaction rate about the Housing Loans **(0.817)**
- Satisfaction rate about the Productivity Bonus **(0.804)**
- Satisfaction rate about the Vehicle Loans **(0.796)**
- Response rate about Recreational facilities/sports **(0.782)**
- Drinking water facilities **(0.758)**

- Satisfaction rate about the Meritorious Service Awards given by Indian Railways to their children **(0.743)**
- Merit Scholarships provided by CCS and Railways Women’s Organization to their children **(0.706)**
- different welfare measures provided by Indian Railways **(0.627)**
- Retirement benefits like pension, gratuity... etc **(0.560)**

Therefore, this factor is appropriately named as **Fringe benefit services.**

The second factor consist of-

- satisfaction levels on Railway Staff Quarters **(0.843)**
- Vehicle Parking facilities in office **(0.788)**
- Satisfaction rate about Library facilities to their children **(0.745)**
- Response on Indian Railways PTO’s **(0.733)**
- Satisfaction towards Privilege Passes **(0.683)**
- satisfaction rate about Medical facilities **(0.635)**
- Satisfaction on Housing projects undertaken by IRWO **(0.631)**
- welfare measures of Indian Railways when compared to other organizations like Defense, Airways, APSRTC **(0.613)**
- Canteen facilities provided in office **(0.609)**

Therefore, this factor is appropriately named as **supportive privileges.**

The third factor consist of –

- Satisfaction rate about Cooperative Credit Society **(0.830)**
- Satisfaction rate about the Student passes to their children **(0.820)**

- satisfaction levels about Railway Schools **(0.776)**
- Feelings about Railway Junior Colleges **(0.738)**
- Satisfaction levels on Degree Colleges **(0.734)**
- Response rate about Welfare measures to women **(0.715)**
- Satisfaction rate about the Function Halls **(0.606)**

Therefore, this factor is appropriately named as **educational facilities**

Factor analysis shows the three predominant factors such as **Fringe benefit services, supportive privileges and educational facilities** are indispensable to satisfy the employees in Railways. In particular, Fringe benefit services to the employees equip them in a serene and tranquil atmosphere and high satisfaction.

Table: 9 MEAN, STD. DEVIATION AND CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

Components	Mean	Std. Deviation	Chi-Square	df	Asymp. Sig.
Satisfaction towards Privilege Passes	3.0267	.65374	278.347 ^a	3	.000
Response on Indian Railways PTO's	2.9233	.64719	339.067 ^a	3	.000
satisfaction levels on Railway Staff Quarters	2.1500	.71358	298.320 ^a	3	.000
satisfaction levels about Railway Schools	2.5667	1.00445	171.947 ^a	3	.000
Feelings about Railway Junior Colleges	2.6300	1.05680	122.640 ^a	3	.000
Satisfaction levels on Degree Colleges	2.6500	1.05414	111.120 ^a	3	.000

satisfaction rate about Medical facilities	2.1400	.85018	86.880 ^a	3	.000
Response rate about Welfare measures to women	2.6167	.96929	183.867 ^a	3	.000
Satisfaction rate about Cooperative Credit Society	3.3267	.99830	219.307 ^a	3	.000
Response rate about Recreational facilities/sports	2.8600	1.06341	84.133 ^a	3	.000
Satisfaction rate about Library facilities to their children	2.2533	.75125	172.107 ^a	3	.000
Satisfaction rate about the Function Halls	2.4800	.80732	121.920 ^a	3	.000
Merit Scholarships provided by CCS and Railways Women's Organization to their children	2.3533	1.18596	24.427 ^a	3	.000
Satisfaction rate about the Student passes to their children	3.4367	.90298	269.413 ^a	3	.000
Satisfaction on Housing projects undertaken by IRWO	2.4333	1.09371	78.987 ^a	3	.000
Satisfaction rate about the Meritorious Service Awards given by Indian Railways to their children	2.6400	1.15825	36.960 ^a	3	.000
Satisfaction rate about the Productivity Bonus	2.4967	1.31749	81.093 ^a	3	.000

Satisfaction rate about the Housing Loans	2.9033	1.06353	165.093 ^a	3	0.000
Satisfaction rate about the Vehicle Loans	2.9600	1.06561	145.653 ^a	3	0.000
Satisfaction levels towards the Festival advance /Loan	2.9067	.94212	141.973 ^a	3	0.000
Vehicle Parking facilities in office	2.4867	.87505	339.067 ^a	3	0.000
Retirement benefits like pension, gratuity... et	2.8867	.81406	96.053 ^a	3	0.000
welfare measures of Indian Railways when compared to other organizations like Defense, Airways, APSRTC.....etc	2.4367	.86515	80.667 ^a	3	0.000
different welfare measures provided by Indian Railways	2.3800	.70989	185.440 ^a	3	0.000
feelings about those Indian Railways in No.1 in providing excellent welfare measures to its employees as a whole	2.4900	1.33761	91.760 ^a	3	0.000
Canteen facilities provided in office	2.3233	.93544	47.600 ^a	3	0.000
Lunch Room facilities	2.7667	1.01768	152.587 ^a	3	0.000
Drinking water facilities	3.0033	1.04257	116.827 ^a	3	0.000

The mean scores computed in Table 4 are based on weighted average method. The mean values represent somewhat positive level of organizational climate in the organization. Among all the factors the Satisfaction towards Privilege Passes has got highest mean value of

3.02. This means respondents are highly satisfied with the Satisfaction towards Privilege Passes in the Indian railways. The notable point is that despite the higher mean value, Satisfaction towards Privilege Passes in railways, std. deviation is highly accurate, the above table also provides the X² analysis of all the corresponding variables, by analyzing the mean scores, it is observed that the variables all are significant at the 0.001 per cent .the variables are have positive relationship with employee welfare facilities in the Indian railways.

To test the Null Hypotheses researcher conducted the chi-square analysis of the variables it shows that all the variables are significant at 0.05 per cent level. By the analysis **the researcher rejected the null hypotheses** and the employees are highly satisfied with the welfare facilities of Indian railways.

CONCLUSIONS:

On the whole employees are satisfied with welfare measures provided by Indian Railways. Railway employees rate their organization as No.1 in providing excellent welfare measures. We can conclude that Indian railways is No.1 in providing welfare measures because no other organization is providing so many welfare measures and also because railway employees say so. Employees are satisfied with some welfare measures and they are not satisfied with some welfare measures. Employees are satisfied with passes, PTOs, educational facilities, canteen, drinking, water facilities etc. employees are not satisfied with retirement benefits, productivity bonus, festival advance, parking facilities etc

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

- Lack of information about Welfare Measures.
- Unable to interact with all the employees.
- Problem with confidential information
- Unable to obtain the proper feedback because the limited time period and busy schedule of the employees.

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